

SEMANTIC, STRUCTURAL AND EXPRESSIVE-STYLISTIC CLASSIFICATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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ABSTRACT

The article researches the fact that phraseological units are considered in three directions: as part of the semantic, structured, expressive stylistic system, the basis of the formation of which are different linguistic processes. Phraseological expressions are only phrases with literal the value of the components. The phraseological expressions include numerous English proverbs and sayings that apply in the literal sense, do not have a figurative allegorical meaning The subject of the article is semantic and structural properties, phraseological units, with the meaning of human intelligence. Article also provides the study the concept of "phraseological unit" and its main characteristics, consider the existing classifications of phraseological units.

INTRODUCTION

During the years of independence deep structural and substantial reforms and transformations in the system of higher education has taken place in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Main purpose of these reforms was to provide the adequate place of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the world community.

Indeed, it was impossible to provide the independent economy, social and political stability, and development of intellectual and spiritual potential of the nation without rebuilding the system of education and upbringing. The state policy in the field of education that could transform it into the priority sphere has been developed and conducted.

Today there is no need to prove that the 21st century is commonly acknowledged to be the century of globalization and vanishing borders, the century of information and communication technologies and the Internet, the century of ever growing competition worldwide and in the global market.

Phraseologisms are special units of the language, which reflect the cultural identity of the people. They indirectly reflect the view people, social system, ideology of their era. The phraseological wealth of any language is the property of its folk national linguistic consciousness. Most phraseological units cannot be translated into other languages: each nation manifests in them its own nature, the usual figurative manner of speech. The impact of

phraseological units gives the language the brightness of the features of the national character and a unique flavor, which distinguishes one from the other both the languages of centuries-old culture and the literary languages that are newly formed by writing. The English language is very rich in phraseological units. His phraseological system captures the vast historical experience of the people, it reflects the life and culture of the nation. Getting acquainted with a foreign language, a person simultaneously penetrates into a new national culture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There are various methods of systematizing phraseological units. Linguists have not yet developed a single principle for the classification of phraseological units. We will consider several classifications phraseological units of the English language offered by different authors.

Semantic classification of phraseological units. The most widely known is the classification of Academician V.V.Vinogradov [12, 141]. In accordance with it, all phraseological units from the point of view of semantic fourteen technical fusion of components are divided into three categories: phraseological fusion, phraseological unity, phraseological combinations.

It is well known that phraseological units appear from a free combination words, which is used in a figurative sense. Of course over time the portability is forgotten, erased, and the combination becomes stable. Depending on how erased the nominative meanings of the components of the phraseological unit, how strong the figurative meaning is in them, V.V. Vinogradov and divides them into three types: "phraseological adhesions, phraseological unity and phraseological combinations." Let us analyze these types of phraseological units in use for modern English language. [12,156]

Phraseological adhesions. Phraseological adhesions, or idioms, are completely indivisible, indecomposable stable combinations, the general meaning of which does not depend on the meaning of their constituent words: kick the bucket (colloquial) - to bend, die; = stretch your legs; send smb. to Coventry -boycott someone, stop communicating with anyone; at bay - hunted down, in a hopeless position; be at smb.'s beck and call - to be always ready for services; = to run errands; to rain cats and dogs - pouring like a bucket (about rain); be all thumbs - be awkward, awkward; Kilkenny cats are deadly enemies. Phraseological adhesions occurred on the basis of figurative meanings of their components, but as a result, these figurative values became incomprehensible from the point of view modern language. "The imagery of phraseological adhesions is revealed only historically. " For example, the words "bay" meaning "dead end" and "beck" - "wave of the hand" are archaisms and are not used anywhere except for the phraseological unit given above. Or, for example, the expression to be all thumbs was historically formed from the expression one's fingers are all thumbs. We consider a similar thing in the phraseological units of Kilkenny cats (which, apparently, dates back to the legend of a fierce struggle between the cities of Kilkenny and Irishtown in the 17th century, which led to their ruin) and send smb. to Coventry (in the book Clarendon's "The History of the Great Rebellion and Civil Wars in England" tells that during the English Revolution there was a prison in the city of Coventry, which contained exiled royalists. [3,230]

Consequently, in phraseological adhesions, the connection between direct and figurative meanings has been destroyed, the figurative has become the main thing for them. That is why phraseological splices are difficult to translate into other languages.

Phraseological adhesions have a number of characteristic features:

1. their composition may include the so-called necroticism - words that nowhere, except for this splicing, are not used, are incomprehensible as a result this from the point of view of modern language;
2. the structure of adhesions includes archaisms;
3. they are syntactically indivisible;
4. in them, in most cases, the permutation of the components is unacceptable;
5. they are characterized by impermeability - do not admit to their structure auxiliary words.

Losing its free lexical meaning, "... words that enter into the composition of a phraseological splicing, turn into components of a complex a lexical unit that matches the meaning of a particular word."

Consequently, many phraseological splices are synonymous with the words:

kick the bucket - to die; send smb. To Coventry - to ignore, etc. But not worth it forget that, as mentioned in the chapter on the equivalence of phraseological unit word, from the point of view of stylistics PhU and the word are far from each other.

Phraseological unity. Phraseological unity is such a stable combination of words in which, in the presence of a single figurative meaning, clearly retains the features of the semantic separation of components: to spill the beans - give a secret; to burn bridges - burn bridges; to have other fish to fry - to have more important things to do; to throw dust into smb.'s eyes - speak teeth; to burn one's fingers - get burned on something; to throw mud at smb. - pour mud; to be narrow in the shoulders - do not understand jokes; to paint the devil blacker than he is - to exaggerate the colors; to put a spoke in smb.'s wheel - put a spoke in wheel ; to hold one's cards close to one's chest - hold something in secret, do not divulge anything, keep quiet, ~ keep your tongue out teeth; to gild refined gold - to gild pure gold, try to improve, decorate something already good enough; to paint the lily - tint the color of a lily, try to improve or decorate something that doesn't need in improvement.

"Phraseological unity is somewhat close to phraseological mergers in their imagery, metaphoricity." But unlike phraseological adhesions, where the figurative content is revealed only diachronically, in phraseological units, imagery, portability understood from the point of view of modern language. V.V.Vinogradov notes expressiveness is a characteristic feature only of phraseological unity. "The connection between the components of phraseological unity is motivated, metaphorization is clearly felt." To understand the phraseological unity, it is necessary to perceive its components in a figurative sense. For example, the meaning of the expression makes a mountain out of a molehill is to do from an elephant fly, i.e. greatly embellish something (literally, make a mountain from a mound of a mole's mink), is revealed only if the word molehill is considered to mean "something insignificant, small", and the word mountain is "something very big". As part of phraseological there are no words that are not clear from the point of view of modern language.

Characteristic features of phraseological units:

1. bright expressiveness and the resulting possibility of convergence with simultaneously existing phrases (compare: to throw dust into smb.'s eyes, to be narrow in the shoulders, to burn one's fingers, to burn bridges);
2. saving the semantics of individual components (to put a spoke in smb.'s wheel);
3. inadmissibility of exchanging some components with others (to hold one's cards close to one's chest);
4. emotionally expressive coloration plays a decisive role (to throw dust into smb.'s eyes, to paint the devil blacker than he is);
5. the ability to enter into synonymous relationships with individual words, or other phraseological units (to gild refined gold = to paint the lily).

Phraseological combinations. Phraseological combinations are stable turns, which include words with both free and phraseologically related meaning: a bosom friend is a bosom friend, a pitched battle is a fierce battle, (to have) a narrow escape - miraculously escape, to frown one's eyebrows - frown eyebrows, Adam's apple - Adam's apple, a Sisyfean labor - Sisyphus labor, rack one's brains - to puzzle (think hard, remember), to pay attention to smb. - to draw attention to someone, etc.

Unlike phraseological mergers and phraseological unities, having integral indivisible meaning, "phraseological combinations are characterized by semantic decomposition". In this respect, they come close to free phrases.

Characteristic features of phraseological combinations:

1. the variance of one of the components is permissible in them (a bosom friend is a bosom friend, a bosom buddy is a bosom friend);
2. Possible synonymous replacement of the pivot word (a pitched battle - a fierce battle, a fierce battle - a fierce battle);
3. the inclusion of concepts is permissible (he frowned his thick eyebrows, he frowned thick eyebrows);
4. permutation of components is permissible (a Sisyfean labor - Sisyphus labor, a Sisyphus labor of Sisyphus - labor of Sisyphus);
5. the free use of one of the components and the associated use of another (a bosom friend is a bosom friend: a bosom friend is not maybe the enemy or someone else).

The advancement of reproducibility in the form of the main feature of phraseological units allowed Professor N.M. Shansky to develop further the classification academician V.V. Vinogradov. As a result, N.M. Shansky identifies the fourth type of phraseological units - the so-called "phraseological expressions". [Shansky 1964: 24]

Phraseological expressions. Phraseological expressions are such stable in their composition and application of phraseological phrases, which consist entirely from words with "free nominative meaning and semantically divisible." Their only feature is reproducibility: they are used as prepared speech units with a stable lexical composition and specific semantics. Phraseological expressions are only phrases with literal the value of the components. The phraseological expressions include numerous English proverbs and sayings that apply in the literal sense, do not have a figurative allegorical meaning: live and learn - live and learn; better untaught than ill taught - it is better to be an uneducated than a wrong scientist;

many men, many mind - how many heads, so many minds; easier said than done -easier said than done; nothing is impossible to a willing heart - whoever wants it will get it.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural classification of phraseological units. N.M. Shansky distinguishes the following typical groups: "adjective + noun" [9, 23]. Noun and adjective can be semantically are equal and both are meaning-making components: smart Aleckallznayka, smart guy, rara avis-white crow (rare bird), a clear head-bright head,clear mind.

The semantic component denotes a noun, the adjective is used as an insignificant term with an expressive character: "a garden head, a jester of a pea,Babylonian pandemonium, green longing." "Noun + genitive noun" Such phraseological turns of meaning and syntactic functions are equivalent to a noun:

"apple of discord –apple contention, point of view - point of view, the palm of supremacy - palm. Words in such phrases are semantically equal. "Noun +prepositional form of the noun".

These phraseological units in the lexical and grammatical relation are correlated with the noun, in all dependent components are unchangeable, and additional ones form different case forms, have a strictly arranged order of distribution of components: "the struggle for life - fight for survival, running on the spot - running on the spot, it's in the bag - in the bag.

"Preposition + name adjective + noun" In terms of lexical and grammatical meaning and syntactic use in a sentence, these phraseological units are equivalent to an adverb, their constituent words are semantically equal, the order of distribution of components is fixed: "in seventh heaven - to be on top of the world,from time immemorial - from time immemorial."

"Case-prepositional form of a noun + genitive form of a noun" These phrases can be adverbial or attributive, they contain the order of distribution of the components of the phraseological unit: "For all time – during twenty-four hours, to the innermost of one's heart - to the core, in Adam's birthday suit - in Adam's suit, in the arms of Morpheus - in the arms of Morpheus, worth one's weight in gold is worth its weight in gold."

"Prepositional-case form of a noun + prepositional form of a noun".

Phraseologisms of this group in terms of lexical and grammatical meaning and syntactic functions are equivalent to an adverb, in which nouns are tautologically repeated, the words that form them are semantically are equal, the order of distribution of the components is fixed: "from morning till night - from dawn to dawn, from cover to cover - from cover to cover, year after year - from year to year, young and old alike - from young to old."

"Verb + noun". Phraseologisms of this group are mainly verb predictive and in a sentence are indicated in the role of a predicate, the order distribution of components and their semantic relationship can be different: "drive home - bring to mind, make a fool - play the fool, act the fool - to play the fool, to play the fool – to play the fool.

"Verb + adverb". Phraseological turns are verbal and in a sentence are denoted in the predicate function, the components are semantically always equal, the order of distribution of the components can be direct and inverse: to see through someone - "to see through, to put one's foot into it - to get in a mess, to go to waste - to waste in vain."

"Verbal participle + noun". Phraseologisms of this type are equivalent to an adverb, in a sentence they act as a circumstance, the order of the components is fixed: "With folded hands - sitting on one's hands, slack one's work - slack."

"Constructions with creative unions" The components of a phraseological unit are homogeneous members' sentences expressed by words of the same part of speech, the order of distribution of components is fixed: "here and there - here and there, pell-mell - at random, sighs and groans - sighs and sighs." "Constructions with subordinate unions". [7]

According to the lexical and grammatical meaning, such phraseological units are adverbial, in which the order of the arrangement of the components is fixed, in the beginning is always a union: "Like a bolt from the blue - Like a thunder among the clear sky, as like as two peas in a pot - like two drops of water, bare as a bone.

"Constructions with negation not". According to the lexical and grammatical meaning, such phraseological units are verbal or adverbial, perform the function of a predicate or circumstance in a sentence, the components are semantically equal with a fixed arrangement order: "be (down) in the dumps - not at ease, not of this world - not of this world."

Expressive - stylistic classification of phraseological units. N.M. Shansky

divides the following groups of phraseological phrases with the point of view of their expressive and stylistic properties: [9, 25]

... interstyle

... colloquial

... book

... archaisms and historicisms

The stylistic division of phraseological units covers "evaluatively - emotionally expressive characteristics that they acquire (phraseological units) as a result of their preferred and even exclusive use in those rather than other spheres and areas of human communication". The use of many phraseological phrases is to some extent limited by the framework of a certain style of language (to have mercy on someone - to let the soul go to repentance - belonging to colloquial speech, spring torrents - spring waters, to go to one's eternal rest - to fall asleep eternal sleep - belonging to the book speech). Many phraseological turns not only name this or that phenomenon of objective reality, but also indicate a certain attitude of the speaker to this phenomenon (disapproval, affection, irony, rhetoric, etc.)

Interstyle phraseological turns. Interstyle phraseological turns are "stable combinations words. Widespread and used in all styles of the language. "Interstyle phraseological units do not have any assessment: from the bottom one's heart - from the bottom of my heart, to keep one's word - keep the word, secret vote - secret ballot, from time to time - from time to time.

Conversational and everyday phraseological turnover. Colloquial everyday phraseological turns - "these are constant combinations of words, mainly or exclusively used in oral speech. "They have a figurative character and are distinguished by an expressive coloring (affectionate, abusive, ironic, contemptuous, playful, etc.): to take the edge off one's hunger - to freeze the worm, to play a dirty upon smb - put a pig.

Book phraseological turns. Book phraseological turns are "stable combinations of words, predominantly or exclusively used in written speech."

They differ in the sphere of use (written speech) and "increased" expressivestylistic coloring (bookish, solemn, pathetic, poetic, etc.): quirk of fate - a game of fate, split second – in blink of an eye. [5,28]

Phraseological archaisms and historicisms. Phraseological historicisms - "these are phraseological turns that have come out of active use in connection with the disappearance of the corresponding phenomenon of reality." For example:

Dutch bargain is a deal made in a drunken state, dutch courage is the courage of a drunken man, dutch treat is a treat in a club, in dutch is to be in trouble, talk like dutch uncle-read morals. [8,116]

Phraseological archaisms - "these are phraseological phrases that have come out of active use in connection with their displacement by other stable combinations or individual words that turned out to be more suitable for expressing the corresponding concepts." For example: at bay - hunted down, in a hopeless position; be at smb.'s beck and call - to be always ready for services; = to run errands;

CONCLUSION

Summarizing what has been said, we can draw the following conclusions about the interpretation of phraseological units in linguistics. Phraseologism is a semantically related combination of words and sentences, "which are not produced in accordance with the general laws of choice and combination of words when organizing statements, but are reproduced in speech in a fixed ratio semantic structure and a certain lexical and grammatical composition". In other words, as the main characteristics of phraseological unity, the reproducibility of the linguistic unit is noted, its constancy composition and idiomatic meaning with varying degrees of revision.

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